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Research Article

**SCREENING FOR MICROORGANISMS WITH A
POTENTIAL FOR PHOSPHATE SOLUBILIZATION**

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Article Received: February 2020**Accepted:** March 2020**Published:** April 2020**Abstract:**

Rhizosphere and non-rhizosphere soil analyses of Lahore horticultural fields and surrounding areas were collected for the disconnection of phosphate-solvent microorganisms. Analyses of soil treated with herbicides were also carried out. Soils treated with herbicides such as Pendimethalin, Trifluralin, Ijaza 13, Squadron were examined for phosphate solubilizers. Our current research was conducted at Jinnah Hospital, Lahore from October 2018 to September 2019. These soils did not contain many bacterial species that could solubilize phosphate. These species were predominantly from the family Bacillus and Pseudomonas. Among the parasites separated from these soils were types of Aspergillus and Penicillium. The amount of phosphate solubilizers in these treated soils was less than in untreated soils. Nevertheless, trifluralin-treated soils contained a moderate number of phosphates solubilizers. Of the 19 confines, 2 bacterial and 3 contagious companies indicating a relatively higher solubilization capacity on Petoskey agar screening and Petoskey soup containing TCP were selected for representation.

Key words: Screening, Microorganisms, Phosphate Solubilization.

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INTRODUCTION:

Phosphorus is one of the basic components of every organic element. It is related to some fundamental capacities and is responsible for some attributes of plant development, for example, the use of sugars and starch, photosynthesis, the arrangement of nuclei and cell division, the arrangement of fats and egg whites, cell organization and the exchange of heredity. Microbial solubilization of inorganic phosphate mixtures is of incredible monetary importance for plant sustenance. The solubilization of phosphorus by microscopic and growing organisms plays an important role in the transformation of insoluble phosphate mixtures, e.g. rock phosphate, bone meal and basic slag, and especially artificially fixed soil phosphorus, into an accessible structure. These life forms assimilate phosphorus and aim to release a huge segment of solvent phosphate in excess of their own preconditions. Solubilization is not limited to calcium salts, but iron, aluminum, magnesium, manganese and various phosphates are also monitored. A few microorganisms responsible for the solubilization of insoluble phosphates have been found in extraordinary numbers in rhizosphere separations from the soil. It has been established that strong convergences of P, Ca and different components occur in vesicular-arbuscular mycorrhizal organisms due to the creation of oxalic corrosion by VAM parasites. The chelation effects of the microbial components and different types of natural soil problems were verified by Konnikova. The Soviet Union used the lifestyle of *Bacillus megatherium* var. phosphatic as an inoculant for phosphorus solubilization. Canada used *Penicillium Balaji* with the trade name Provide. Life forms solubilizing phosphorus in this manner began to be used as inoculants to extend the availability of P to publishing in these countries and prompted improved planning of inoculums that are known primarily as phosphorus microorganisms.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The Petoskey carrier with the accompanying arrangement was used: glucose 10 g, tricalcium phosphate (TCP) 5 g, ammonium sulphate 0,5 g, sodium chloride 0,2 g, magnesium sulphate 0,1 g, potassium chloride 0,2 g, separated yeast 0,5 g, manganese sulphate and ferrous sulphate in trace amounts, agar 18 g, w/w 1 liter, pH adjusted to $7,0 \pm 0,2$. Our current research was conducted at Jinnah Hospital, Lahore from October 2018 to September 2019. These soils did not contain many bacterial species that could solubilize phosphate. These species were predominantly from the family *Bacillus* and *Pseudomonas*. Among the parasites separated from these soils were types of *Aspergillus* and *Penicillium*. An enhancement culture system was used for the removal of phosphate solubilizers. 1 g of soil was added to a cup containing 100 ml of

Petoskey juice. Three progressive exchanges were carried out week by week intermittently to improve the medium. At this time, the phosphate solubilizers were isolated by looping the last decanter on a strong Petoskey agar medium. Provinces where no phosphate solubilization was acquired within 4-6 days were selected and transferred to a crisp medium. Subculture was continued until unaltered societies were obtained on similar media when grown at 30°C. The unaltered societies were maintained on the slope of the Petoskey agar at 4°C.

Screening of Phosphate Solubilizers:

Solubilization of TCP on solid support:

All disengaged strains were independently immunized on Petoskey agar plates. These strains were vaccinated punctually on the plates under aseptic conditions. The plates were incubated at $28 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ for 3-5 days and the solubilization zone around the state was monitored. Those that demonstrated the solubilization zone were endangered to be phosphate solubilizers and were tested for solubilization in a fluid medium.

Solubilization of TCP in a fluid medium:

All of the selected disconnectors on Petoskey agar and stored on the Petoskey slope were independently immunized in a 250 ml Erlenmeyer decanter containing 100 ml of Petoskey broth with 1.2 ml of inoculum in each. All sections hatched at $28 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ for 21 days under static conditions and were shaken once at 12-hour intervals. The uninoculated medium was filled as control. 10.0 ml of medium was removed every three days and centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 20 minutes. The supernatant was examined for its water-soluble P content according to the technique given by Jackson (1973). The final pH of the medium was estimated using a computerized pH meter.

Determination of significant solubilizers:

From the discharges selected, five living beings that demonstrated maximum solubilization on strong media such as in fluid soup were chosen to decide on their solubilizing action on phosphate in three sets. Each decanter was immunized with 1.0 ml of inoculum. The rest of the strategy was followed as discussed in the solubilization of TCP in fluid media. Of the five separators selected, the one that allowed maximum solubilization of phosphorus in the juices was chosen and submitted for further examination.

Crop Maintenance:

After cleaning the Pikovskaya agar medium, it was allowed to cool until the temperature dropped to 60°C. At this time, 50 µg/ml of cycloheximide was added aseptically to protect the plates from contagious stains and subsequently the culture was maintained on the plates.

Estimation of soluble Phosphorus: Osmond method (Jackson, 1973) has been extensively adapted for phosphorus determinations.

Determination of pH:

The pH of the lifestyle supernatant was estimated using a computerized pH meter. Corn rhizosphere soils treated with different nitrogen sources were also read for phosphate solubilizers. It was found that soils with 100% N prescribed by inorganic composts contained many times more phosphate solubilizers than untreated soils. Soils treated with nitrogen and phosphorus fertilizers were 12 to 13 times richer in phosphate solubilizers. This information was determined by comparing analyses of treated soils and untreated controls. Soil analyses collected from rhizosphere and non-rhizosphere soils of various yields from Lahore and surrounding areas were independently vaccinated in the Pikovskaya stock. For the improvement of phosphate solubilizers, three progressive exchanges of this juice were carried out intermittently, week by week. At this time, a culture loop was drawn on solid plates. Initially, 19 different disconnections were chosen for P solubilization because all these confines could produce solubilization zones on the

adjusted Pikovskaya agar plates (Gupta et al., 1996). Of the 19 isolates, 3 bacterial and 4 parasitic societies showing relatively greater solubilization capacity when screened on Pikovskaya agar and Pikovskaya soup containing TCP were selected for representation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS:

On the basis of their morphological and social characteristics, the two bacterial disconnects were distinguished as *Bacillus* and *Citrobacter* types, while the three parasitic species were recognized as *Aspergillus*, *Mucor* and *Penicillium* [6-8]. Before choosing *Citrobacter* for further investigation, the 7 isolates were spot-immunized on Pikovskaya agar containing tricalcium phosphate. The phosphate solubilizers make it possible to delimit clear areas around the provinces due to the disintegration of the phosphate [9]. As shown in Table 1, the area of solubilization was the most important for *Citrobacter* compared to the other four strains chosen. The solubilization zone was 10 mm for *Citrobacter* and 8 mm for *Bacillus*. The solubilization zone for *Aspergillus* was 8 mm. For *Penicillium* and *Mucor*, the size of the zone was 8 mm and 5 mm individually [10].

Table 1: Phosphate solubilizing zone observed on Modified Pikovskaya's agar after 7 days by different isolates:

Isolates	Colony diameter (mm)	Phosphate solubilizing zones
Bacillus	8	7
Citrobacter	10	9
Aspergillus	12	8
Mucor	12	3
Penicillium	15	6

Fluid solubilization with TCP as the source of P was read in addition for the 5 life forms. The solubilization pattern of TCP followed by these 5 segregates is as follows (Table 2).

TCP (mg % P₂O₅): *Citrobacter* (168.80) > *Penicillium* (87.76) > *Bacillus* (66.81) > *Aspergillus* (58.17) > *Mucor* (57.58)

Table 2: Solubilization of TCP by 5 different isolates during growth on Pikovskaya's broth

Organism	(mg % P ₂ O ₅)	pH of the broth	Day of max Solubilization
Bacillus		4.91	3
Citrobacter	64.8	4.13	6
Aspergillus	167.7	5.40	3
Mucor	59.16	4.69	9
Penicillium	55.58 86.75	5.13	9

CONCLUSIONS:

The living being was examined from various soil analyses of the neighboring region. Among the different acquired confines, the one with the greatest movement of phosphate solubilization was chosen for further examination. An attempt was made to recognize the life form by examining its morphological and biochemical properties and it was distinguished as a *Citrobacter* species. It was later distinguished as *Citrobacter Freundi* MTCC 6739 by the MTCC. Screening for living things in native soils may prove to be a better inoculant than those presented.

chromium contaminated agricultural soil. *Chemosphere* 192: 318–327.

REFERENCES:

1. El-Ghit, H.M.A. (2016) Physiological allelopathic effect of aqueous extracts of cucumber, onion to the pea. *J Pharm, Chem Biol Sci* 4: 13–19.
2. Etesami, H., Hosseini, H.M., and Alikhani, H.A. (2014) Bacterial biosynthesis of 1-aminocyclopropane-1-carboxylate (ACC) deaminase, a useful trait to elongation and endophytic colonization of the roots of rice under constant flooded conditions. *Physiol Mol Biol Plants* 20: 425–434.
3. Etesami, H., Alikhani, H.A., and Hosseini, M.H. (2015) Indole-3-acetic acid (IAA) production trait, a useful screening to select endophytic and rhizosphere competent bacteria for rice growth promoting agents. *MethodsX* 2: 72–78.
4. Fatih, H. (2018) A comprehensive overview of onion production: worldwide and Turkey. *IOSR J Agric Vet Sci* 11: 17–27.
5. Felsenstein, J. (1985) Confidence-limits on phylogenies—an approach using the bootstrap. *Evolution* 39: 783–791.
6. Felsenstein, J. (1993) PHYLIP (Phylogeny Inference Package), version 3.5c. URL <http://www0.nih.gov/~jun/research/phylip/main.html>.
7. Funke, G., Aravena-Roman, M., and Frodl, R. (2005) First description of *Curtobacterium* spp. isolated from human clinical specimens. *J Clin Microbiol* 43: 1032–1036.
8. Gamalero, E., and Glick, B.R. (2015) Bacterial modulation of plant ethylene levels. *Plant Physiol* 169: 13–22.
9. Guiñazú, L.B., Andrés, J.A., Rovera, M., Balzarini, M., and Rosas, S.B. (2013) Evaluation of rhizobacterial isolates from Argentina, Uruguay and Chile for plant growth-promoting characteristics and antagonistic activity towards *Rhizoctonia* sp. and *Macrophomina* sp. in vitro. *Eur J Soil Biol* 54: 69–77.
10. Gupta, P., Kumar, V., Usmani, Z., Rani, R., and Chandra, A. (2018) Phosphate solubilization and chromium (VI) remediation potential of *Klebsiella* sp. strain CPSB4 isolated from the